

Women's Knowledge, Attitude & Practice Regarding Breastfeeding Attending in Pediatric OPD at 250 Bedded General Hospital, Jashore, Bangladesh

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ABSTRACT

For the most majority of children in developing nations, breastfeeding is thought to be the most vital factor that influences whether they will live or die, although the pattern of breastfeeding and exclusive breastfeeding are more crucial factors, which are frequently neglected by most mothers. This descriptive type of cross-sectional study was conducted among 384 respondents from 250 bedded General Hospital, Jashore, Bangladesh to find out the factors influencing Women's Knowledge, attitudes, and practices regarding breastfeeding who are visiting Pediatric OPD from October, 2021 to Marc, 2022. Respondents were enrolled in the study using Purposive sampling technique. Data was collected by face to face interview with a semi-structured questionnaire. Here, 53.0% women's knowledge on breast feeding was Good as well as 41.0% women's knowledge was Fair and 6.0% women's knowledge was Poor on the other hand 22.0% women's Attitude on breast feeding was Good as well as 54.0% women's Attitude was Fair and 24.0% women's Attitude was Poor & 28.0% women's Practice on breast feeding was Good as well as 39.0% women's Practice was Fair and 33.0% women's Practice was Poor. While there was typically good knowledge about breastfeeding, there was still inadequate practice. Breastfeeding expertise and mothers' employment position were revealed to be modifiable factors that predicted exclusive breastfeeding.

KEYWORDS: Knowledge, Attitude, Practice, Breastfeeding, Women.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The best method of feeding infants is considered as breastfeeding, which is the basis of life [1]. Breast milk offers the fundamental building blocks for optimum growth and development and contains the ideal ratio of readily available, easily digestible nutrients for growth. It is the public health strategy that reduces newborn and child morbidity and mortality at the lowest possible cost. Given the well-established advantages of nursing for the health of both mother and child, WHO recommends exclusive breastfeeding during the first six months following delivery, followed by continued breastfeeding for at least two years beyond it [2]. According to estimates, breastfeeding can boost a child's tolerance to all preventive treatments and save 1.4 million lives in impoverished nations [3]. Compared to non-breastfed newborns, breastfed infants have a six-fold better chance of surviving their first six months.

Breast milk reduces the risk of diarrhoea and acute respiratory infection, two major newborn deaths, as well as other infectious diseases [4]. In underdeveloped nations with high illness loads and restricted access to sanitary facilities and clean water, the potential effects of effective breastfeeding habits are especially significant. Infants who are not nursed in underdeveloped nations are even more likely to pass away. It was shown that mortality among non-breastfed newborns increased by 25% in a recent study of post-neonatal mortality in the United States. In the UK, the Millennium Cohort Survey found that breastfeeding exclusively for six months was associated with a 53 percent drop in hospital admissions for diarrhoea and a 27 percent drop in respiratory tract infections [5].

Despite the benefits of breastfeeding for newborns, babies, and mothers, which have been demonstrated by substantial evidence from both developed and developing countries, the

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rate of exclusive breastfeeding (EBF) keeps declining in both these two groups of nations [6]. In wealthy nations, about 38% of infants younger than six months are exclusively breastfed, while only 39% of infants between 20 and 23 months benefit from the practice of continuing breastfeeding.

Understanding the breastfeeding knowledge and attitude of mothers and factors influencing their breastfeeding practices is important. Many studies were conducted worldwide and this study to be conducted in the Jashore, Bangladesh. Our study was aim to assess knowledge, and attitude of mothers breastfeeding. This study will provide information on mothers' breastfeeding knowledge, and attitude. Also, the results of this study will be communicated to the Ministry of Health & Family Welfare and other relevant stakeholders for future planning and decision-making for improved activities and programs, and it will also serve as a foundation for future research. So, the study was conducted to find out Women's Knowledge, Attitude & Practice regarding Breastfeeding attending in Paediatric OPD at 250 bedded General Hospital, Jashore, Bangladesh.

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1 Study design: Descriptive cross-sectional study.

2.2 Study Setting: Paediatric OPD (Out Patient Department), 250 bedded General Hospital, Jashore, Bangladesh.

2.3 Study period: The study was conducted between October, 2021 to March, 2022.

2.4 Study Sample: The sample size was calculated using a 95% confidence level and 5% error with a response rate of 50%, the sample size adding a 10% drop out rate, 384 nurses were considered to participate in the survey. So, a convenience non-random sample consisted of 384 mothers.

2.5 The inclusion criteria: Women aged 18 years or older. Who had at least one child aged 2 years or younger at the time of the study.

2.6 Tools of the study: Self-administrative questionnaire that was utilized to collect data. Questionnaire divided in to four parts are as follows:

A. consists of socio-demographic characteristics as Age (years), Education, Marital status, Monthly family income (in Taka), Employed, Employment sector (82 persons), Entitled to breastfeeding hours by employer (82 persons), Living with husband and children only, Number of housemaids or nannies, Number of children and Mode of delivery of last child.

B. The Mothers' knowledge was assessed using 12 questions. The majority of the questions were based on the participants' experience with their last child. Answer points were assigned to each question, with one point awarded for each yes response and zero for no or I don't know responses.

Each participant's overall knowledge score was calculated by adding their yes answers together. The knowledge marks were categorised into Poor knowledge ($\leq 50\%$), Fair knowledge (51- 80%), and (> 80) measured Good knowledge.

C. The Mothers' Attitude was assessed using 06 questions. Answer points were assigned to each question, with one point awarded for each yes (Positive Attitude) response and zero for no or I don't know responses. Each participant's overall Attitude score was calculated by adding their positive answers together. The Attitude marks were categorised into Poor Attitude ($\leq 50\%$), Fair Attitude (51- 80%), and (> 80) measured Good Attitude.

D. The Mothers' Practices were assessed using 06 questions. Answer points were assigned to each question, with one point awarded for each yes (Positive) response and zero for no or I don't know responses. Each participant's overall practice score was calculated by adding their positive answers together. The Practices marks were categorised into Poor ($\leq 50\%$), Fair (51- 80%), and (> 80) measured Good.

2.7 Validity and reliability of the study: A board of five academic and health-care experts examined and validated the questionnaire; no comments were made. The questionnaire items had an internal consistency of 0.90 Cronbach's alpha (α), which was considered acceptable.

2.8 Statistical analysis: Data were processed and analyzed using computer software program SPSS version-25. The data present on categorical scale were expressed as frequency and corresponding percentage and compared by chi-square test, while the quantitative data were presented as mean and standard deviation (SD) and compared by student's t-test. Postoperative final outcome were evaluated using confidence interval. For all analyses level of significance was set at 0.05 and p-value < 0.05 was considered significant.

2.9 Data presentation: The observation and findings of the investigation and statistical analysis were presented using appropriate charts, figures, tables, and diagrams. The mean, range, percentage, and standard deviation (SD) were utilized in the case of continuous variables. Cross table and composite graph were employed in the case of categorized variables.

2.10 Ethical considerations: This study was approved by the nursing department, 250 bedded General Hospital, Jashore, Bangladesh. Several strategies were utilized to protect the mother's rights who agreed to participate in this study. First, oral verbal consent of the mothers were obtained prior to the administration of the questionnaire. The mothers were informed of the purpose of the study, and that they had the right to refuse to participate. Also the voluntary nature of participation was stressed as well as confidentiality. Furthermore, the mothers were told that they

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can refrain from answering any questions and they can terminate at any time. Anonymity of the mothers was maintained at all times.

3. RESULT

Table 1. Distribution of the women's according to demographic variables (n=384).

Variables	Characteristics	Frequency	Percent
Age (years)	18-24 years old	42	11.0
	25-29 years old	158	41.0
	30-34 years old	130	34.0
	35-39 years old	31	8.0
	40-44 years old	15	4.0
	≥ 45 years old	8	2.0
Education	No education	13	3.0
	Primary (class I-V)	88	23.0
	Secondary (class VI-X)	197	52.0
	Intermediate or higher	86	22.0
Marital status	Married	373	97.0
	Divorced / Widowed	11	3.0
Monthly family income (in Taka)	< 15,000	123	32.0
	15,000–30,000	179	47.0
	> 30,000	82	21.0
Employed	Yes	82	21.0
	No	279	73.0
	Self-employed	23	6.0
Employment sector (82 persons)	Government	30	37.0
	Private	52	63.0
Entitled to breastfeeding hours by employer (82 persons)	Yes	26	32.0
	No	56	68.0
Living with husband and children only	Yes	272	71.0
	No (Living with relatives)	107	28.0
	No (Separated/Divorced/Widowed)	05	1.0
Number of housemaids or nannies	0	280	73.0
	1	84	22.0
	> 1	20	5.0
Number of children	1	172	45.0
	2–4	198	51.0
	≥ 5	14	4.0
Mode of delivery of last child	Vaginal delivery	227	59.0
	Caesarian section	157	41.0

Table 1 shows that maximum women's age were 25-29 years old 158 (41.0%), education were secondary (class VI-X) 197 (52.0%), marital status were married 373 (97.0%), monthly family income (in Taka) were (15,000–30,000 taka) 179 (47.0), employed were No 279 (73.0%), employment sector were private 52 (63.0%), entitled to breastfeeding

hours by employer was No 56 (68.0%), living with husband and children only were Yes 272 (71.0%), number of housemaids or nannies were (0) 280 (73.0%), number of children were (2–4) 198 (51.0%) and mode of delivery of last child were vaginal delivery 227 (59.0%).

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Table 2. Distribution of the women’s according to Knowledge questionnaire (n=384).

Variables	Correct answer	
	Frequency	Percent
Breastfeeding child ≥ 8 times/day during the 1 st month	215	56.0
Breastfeeding period ≥ 15 min from each breast during the 1 st month	150	39.0
Colostrum is good for child	342	89.0
Breastfeeding is beneficial for both the mother and the child	349	91.0
Children should receive breast milk until ≥ 24 months of age	138	36.0
Complementary food should be introduced at 6 months of age	315	82.0
Breast milk is superior to formula milk in fulfilling child’s necessary dietary requirements	353	92.0
Breast milk is sufficient for child in the first 6 months of life	319	83.0
Breastfeeding decreases the mother’s weight	207	54.0
Breast milk does not lose its benefits when it is pumped out or stored	223	58.0
Pumped breast milk can be stored at room temperature (60 °F–85 °F/15.5 °C–29.4 °C) for up to 8 hours	177	46.0
Pumped breast milk can be stored in the refrigerator (39 °F or colder/3.99 °C or colder) for up to 8 days	104	27.0

Table 2 shows that maximum women’s correct knowledge on Breastfeeding child ≥ 8 times/day during the 1st month were 215 (56.0%), on breastfeeding period ≥ 15 min from each breast during the 1st month were 150 (39.0%), on colostrum is good for child were 342 (89.0%), on breastfeeding is beneficial for both the mother and the child 349 (91.0%), on children should receive breast milk until ≥ 24 months of age 138 (36.0%), complementary food should be introduced at 6 months of age 315 (82.0%), on breast milk is superior to formula milk in fulfilling child’s

necessary dietary requirements were 353 (92.0%), on breast milk is sufficient for child in the first 6 months of life were 319 (83.0%), on breastfeeding decreases the mother’s weight were 207 (54.0%), on breast milk does not lose its benefits when it is pumped out or stored were 223 (58.0%), on pumped breast milk can be stored at room temperature (60 °F–85 °F/15.5 °C–29.4 °C) for up to 8 hours were 177 (46.0%) and Pumped breast milk can be stored in the refrigerator (39 °F or colder/3.99 °C or colder) for up to 8 days were 104 (27.0%).

Figure 1. Distribution of the women’s according to overall knowledge level (n=384).

Figure 1 show that 53.0% women’s knowledge on breast feeding was Good as well as 41.0% women’s knowledge was Fair and 6.0% women’s knowledge was Poor.

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Table 3. Distribution of the women’s according to Attitude questionnaire (n=384).

Variables	Characteristics	Frequency	Percent
Breastfeeding can increase the mother’s weight.	Yes	227	59.0
	No*	81	21.0
	Don’t know	76	20.0
One of the causes of hair loss is breastfeeding.	Yes	119	31.0
	No*	227	59.0
	Don’t know	38	10.0
Pumping breast milk makes it no longer beneficial for the child.	Yes	65	17.0
	No*	219	57.0
	Don’t know	100	26.0
Mothers should stop breastfeeding if they take any type of medication.	Yes	188	49.0
	No*	92	24.0
	Don’t know	104	27.0
Intention to breastfeed future children.	Yes*	361	94.0
	No	8	2.0
	Don’t know	15	4.0
Plan to attend breastfeeding classes in future pregnancy.	Yes	265	69.0
	No*	31	8.0
	Don’t know	88	23.0

Positive attitude*

Table 3 shows that maximum women’s positive attitude on breastfeeding can increase the mother’s weight were 81 (21.0%), on one of the causes of hair loss is breastfeeding were 227 (59.0%), on pumping breast milk makes it no longer beneficial for the child 219 (57.0%), on mothers should stop breastfeeding if they take any type of medication were 92 (24.0%), on intention to breastfeed future children were 361 (94.0%) and Plan to attend breastfeeding classes in future pregnancy were 31 (8.0%).

Figure 2. Distribution of the women’s according to overall attitude level (n=384).

Figure 2 shows that 22.0% women’s Attitude on breast feeding was Good as well as 54.0% women’s Attitude was Fair and 24.0% women’s Attitude was Poor.

Table 3. Distribution of the women’s according to reasons behind adoption of breastfeeding (n = 384)

Variables	Frequency	Percent
Religious background	146	38.0
Healthcare providers	111	29.0
Child health	349	91.0
Media	42	11.0

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Cleanliness and easy preparation	127	33.0
Personal determination or experience	23	6.0
Encouragement from mother/mother-in-law	104	27.0
Encouragement from husband	100	26.0
Other	15	4.0
I don’t know	23	6.0

Table 3 shows women’s reasons behind adoption of breastfeeding. Reason of Religious background were 146 (38.0%), healthcare providers were 111 (29.0%), child health were 349 (91.0%), media were 42 (11.0%), Cleanliness and easy preparation were 127 (33.0%),

personal determination or experience were 23 (6.0%), encouragement from mother/mother-in-law were 104 (27.0%), other were 15 (4.0%) and I don’t know were 23 (6.0%).

Table 4. Distribution of the women’s according to Practices questionnaire (n=384).

Variables	Positive answer	
	Frequency	Percent
Launch of breastfeeding instantly and within the 1st hour of life	288	75.0
Currently breastfeeding the last child and intending to continue until the age of ≥24 months	115	30.0
Exclusively breastfed last child for 6 months	77	20.0
Planning to continue exclusively breastfeeding last child until 6 months of age (for children < 6 months of age)	35	9.0
Child was not given ready-made liquid formula in the hospital	234	61.0
Attended breastfeeding classes during pregnancy	108	28.0

Table 4 shows women’s practices on breastfeeding. Positive practices on launch of breastfeeding instantly and within the 1st hour of life were 288 (75.0%), on currently breastfeeding the last child and intending to continue until the age of ≥24 months were 115 (30.0%), on exclusively breastfed last child for 6 months were 77 (20.0%), on planning to continue

exclusively breastfeeding last child until 6 months of age (for children < 6 months of age) were 35 (9.0%), on child was not given ready-made liquid formula in the hospital were 234 (61.0%) and attended breastfeeding classes during pregnancy were 108 (28.0%).

Figure 3. Distribution of the women’s according to overall practice level (n=384).

Figure 3 shows that 28.0% women’s Practice on breast feeding was Good as well as 39.0% women’s Practice was Fair and 33.0% women’s Practice was Poor.

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4. DISCUSSION

This study's larger exclusive breastfeeding rate at 6 months compared to studies conducted in Saudi Arabia may be explained by the fact that many more women in our study (83.0%) thought breast milk alone sufficed for the infant throughout the first 6 months of life than in a Saudi Arabian study (28%) [7]. Our study indicated that mothers were more likely to practice exclusive breastfeeding for six months if they scored higher on a test of their breastfeeding competence. The fact that maternity leave in the U.A.E. and Saudi Arabia is longer than in the U.S.A. and that it is paid for in full, unlike in the U.S.A., may further contribute to the greater exclusive breastfeeding rate in both countries compared to the U.S.A. [8]. In our study, it was discovered that the later disparities, particularly from mothers and mothers-in-law, had a significant impact on nursing knowledge. Also, women who lived with their family had better attitudes and knowledge about breastfeeding, which may help to further explain the discrepancies. On the other hand, the higher rates of exclusive breastfeeding in Uganda may be related to their culture and tradition surrounding infant feeding: in some regions of Uganda, breastfeeding is the only acceptable method of infant feeding [9], while in others, women who cannot afford formula milk choose to breastfeed [10].

The majority of survey participants (91.0%) stated child health as their main incentive for starting breastfeeding, followed by religious beliefs (38.0%). The main causes were the same in both studies, with child health accounting for 43.7% of the variance and religious background accounting for 17.2% [11]. The similar cultures, religious beliefs, and worldviews of these two nations may help to explain these commonalities. The Islamic teachings in the Holy Quran, which read, "And mothers shall breastfeed their children for two whole years, for those who choose to finish the acceptable duration of breastfeeding," [12] are most likely the source of the relationship between breastfeeding and religious tradition.

In our study, it was found that mothers who were employed were less likely to practice exclusive breastfeeding for 6 months, which is consistent with the findings of several studies [13, 14]. Other studies have shown that inadequate comprehensive maternity leave policies, lack of child care facilities at or near the workplace, rigid time schedules that do not allow for nursing breaks, lack of facilities providing privacy for breast-pumping, and absence of facilities for the refrigeration of pumped breast milk are among the factors that affect breastfeeding practice among working mothers [15, 16]. The effect of these factors is likely to be the reason why most of our participants had shifted to formula feeding by 6 months. In our study, the majority of participants (89.0%) were aware of the advantages of giving colostrum to the kid, just like in two studies from Saudi Arabia (89.3%) [7, 17]. In contrast, 60% of the investigated women

in other regions of India still discard colostrum, according to a recent study [18], while 77% of the moms in the Rajasthan district of India who were assessed did the same [19]. The cultural and religious distinctions between these Indian regions and the United Arab Emirates may help to explain these discrepancies. The majority of respondents (94.0%) expected to breastfeed their future children, which is similar to two studies from Saudi Arabia (90.1%). These similarities could be explained by the similarity between the cultures and worldviews of these two countries. Another study [20] found that this mentality is one of the best indicators of the start and continuation of breastfeeding.

5. CONCLUSIONS

Despite largely positive breastfeeding knowledge, there was still need for improvement in breastfeeding technique. It was discovered that mothers' employment level and breastfeeding expertise are modifiable factors that predict exclusive breastfeeding. Insufficient breast milk production and the baby appearing hungry or unsatisfied after feeding were the most frequent causes for discontinuing breastfeeding. Thus, during pregnancy follow-up appointments, healthcare professionals should educate all women about breastfeeding, especially those with poor educational levels and no prior breastfeeding experience. By giving working mothers extended maternity leaves and paid time off so they can continue breastfeeding their children, solutions should be offered to remove breastfeeding barriers.

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